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COVER ART – The cover art was painted by Jason Poole and depicts a school of Mosasaurs.

A HOLOCENE BEAVER (*CASTOR CANADENSIS*) TUNNEL COMPLEX, CROFTON, ANNE ARUNDEL COUNTY, MARYLAND: THE MOST COMPLEX TUNNEL SYSTEM RECORDED IN THE UNITED STATES

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INTRODUCTION

It is difficult to reconstruct an event that took place over forty years ago (let alone an event you did not participate in) but it is fortunate that an extensive Holocene North American beaver tunnel complex was documented thanks to the efforts of a group of enthusiastic amateur and professional archeologists. The Maryland State Archeologist, Tyler Bastian, wrote a narrative of his involvement with the project (Bastian, 1973). Garry Wheeler Stone, archeologist with the St. Mary's City Commission, wrote a short report of the Commission's investigation and provided photographs and a field sketch map of the tunnel complex (Stone, 1973). William P. Doepkens, a local farmer, naturalist, and amateur archeologist, prepared two reports that comprehensively document the investigation of the tunnel complex (Doepkens, 1979a, and Doepkens et al., 1979). Doepkens also took photographs, and he and his colleague Eric Dennard made drawings of the tunnel complex, as well as made casts of the tooth marks in the complex. In addition, newspaper articles provide some context to the investigation. Finally, William Doepken's son, Bill Doepkens, provided his remembrances of the investigation.

Aside from at least eleven newspaper articles, the unpublished narrative of the investigation of the tunnel complex by the Maryland State Archeologist and two self-published reports on the complex by William P. Doepkens, never circulated within the scientific community, this tunnel complex has never been formally published. The purpose of this paper is to summarize the tunnel complex investigation and provide confirmation that the tunnels were made by the North American beaver, *Castor canadensis*. Unfortunately, there is no organic material to date the age of the tunnel complex, but

it is interpreted as dating from the Holocene Epoch, probably during the early historic period.

The Crofton Tunnel Complex, dug by both claw and incisor, is the largest and best documented example of a beaver tunnel and den complex recorded in the United States. This site would never have been documented without the dedicated effort of concerned local citizens who convinced the developer to delay destruction of the site for research purposes.

OVERVIEW OF THE DISCOVERY

The Crofton Tunnel Complex was discovered by accident on July 9, 1973, during excavation for new townhouses in the Crofton area of Anne Arundel County, Maryland. The tunnel complex was identified within a weathered zone of the Paleocene age Aquia Formation. The tunnels attracted the attention of curiosity seekers, elected officials, amateur archeologists, and scientists from the Smithsonian Institution's Chesapeake Bay Center for Environmental Studies and National Museum of Natural History, Departments of Anthropology, Mammalogy, and Paleobiology; the Maryland Geological Survey; the George Washington University, Department of Anthropology; the St. Mary's City Commission (now Historic St. Mary's City Commission); the Natural History Society of Maryland; the Maryland Wildlife Administration (now Maryland Department of Natural Resources); and the National Geographic Society.

Suggested origins of the tunnel complex at the time included Indian tunnels, Colonial mining tunnels, caves and caverns, natural underground drainage features, and prehistoric burrows dug by sloths, glyptodonts, giant rodents, giant beavers, and wolves.

The terms "Crofton man" and "prehistoric miniman" were used by some media outlets. Tyler Bastian, Maryland State Archeologist, was apparently the first

scientist to suggest that the marks on the walls of the tunnels were made by animals, not humans. Dr. Robert Humphrey,

George Washington University and Mr. George Stuart, National Geographic Society, agreed with Bastian, stating “the caverns [tunnels] were probably the work of a prehistoric rodent of either the Pleistocene or later era.” Drs. Clayton Ray and Nicholas Hotton III, Department of Paleobiology and Dr. Richard Thorington, Jr., Department of Mammalogy, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, determined the tooth marks on the tunnels were made by the common North American beaver, not extinct giant beavers.

The Crofton Tunnel Complex was located in a hillside 73.2 m (240 ft) from the south bank of Beaver Dam Creek, 36.6 m (120 ft) east of Crofton Parkway and 216.4 m (710 ft) west of Davidsonville Road (Maryland Route 424) (Doepkens, 1979a:2, Figure 1). The complex was located at the intersection of Lang Drive and Crofton Parkway, about 1.2 km (0.75 mi) east of Crain Highway (Maryland Route 3), Crofton, Anne Arundel County, Maryland. Beaver Dam Creek is a tributary east of the confluence of the Patuxent River and Little Patuxent River. There are several man-made ponds and lakes in this area today. The estimated elevation of the hill that the tunnel complex was dug into was about 30 feet high based on Diagram 1 in the Doepkens et al. (1979:12) report. A marsh was located approximately 86 feet above sea level and the top of the hill was approximately 118 feet above sea level; the latitude and longitude is approximately 39°00'21.3"N 76°40'48.3"W. Frizzell (2005:Figures 2 and 3) includes photographs of what the tunnel complex area looks like after townhouse development at what is called Crofton Commons.

House numbers 1800-1802-1804-1806-1808-1810-1812 occupy the former tunnel complex location. See Doepkens (1979a:16, Figure 13) for a photograph of townhouse foundations under construction over the tunnel complex location.

The Crofton Tunnel Complex is located in a weathered zone of the Aquia Formation, a shallow marine sand dating from the Paleocene Epoch. The Aquia sands in the Crofton area are deeply weathered so that the typical dark olive-green clayey sand with large amounts of glauconite has been broken down into limonite, which gives the sands reddish-brown stains and crusts (Glaser, 1973). Doepkens (1979a:24) provided the following description, “The upper soils [matrix] are gray-greenish fine sandy clay, often streaked with reddish brown.” The matrix “varied in color, modeled, stained and streaked reddish brown, yellowish, gray pinkish, with a smooth talc-like texture. It could readily be broken and rubbed into dust when dry but was extremely firm when damp or wet and highly resistant to rubbing and water action. Soil samples from the sides of the tunnels at the water level contained 55% sand, 42.4% silt, and 2.6% clay. Presumably, this analysis was conducted by the Maryland Geological Survey, but these percentages were not included in John Glaser’s (1973) one-page summary attached to Bastian’s Narrative Report (1973). Cary Carson, architectural historian with the St. Mary’s City Commission, described the matrix as a fine sandy clay (Doepkens, 1979a:5). John Sands, one of the interns with Carson, recalled the “tunnels were about two feet in diameter and were dug through hard clay. There were scratch marks on the side (appropriate to antler tools) and some sandstone/iron oxide inclusions.”¹

¹ John Sands email to Eshelman, December 1, 2018.

FIGURE 1. View of tunnel complex as exposed by a backhoe. The backhoe bucket teeth marks are visible in the excavation wall. *Baltimore News American* July 26, 1973, photo by James Kelmartin.

TIMELINE OF INVESTIGATION

Individuals from many institutions and organizations were contacted during the investigation of the Crofton Tunnel Complex. They include the Smithsonian Institution's Chesapeake Bay Center for Environmental Studies and National Museum of Natural History, Departments of Anthropology, Mammalogy, and Paleobiology; the Maryland Geological Survey; the George Washington University Department of Anthropology; the St. Mary's City Commission

(now Historic St. Mary's City Commission); the Natural History Society of Maryland; the Maryland Wildlife Administration (now Maryland

Department of Natural Resources) and; the National Geographic Society.² One newspaper reporter referred to the tunnels as made by "Crofton Man" (Sherwood, 1973) and a book author referred the builder of the tunnels as made by "prehistoric miniman" (Brandon, 1978:101).

² See Bastian, 1973 and Doepkens, 1979a for a further discussion of individuals and institutions contacted.

Tyler Bastian, then Maryland State Archeologist, received a phone call on July 13, 1973, about “tunnels” discovered during construction of new townhouses in the Crofton area. The tunnels were first exposed on July 9, 1973, when a bulldozer fell approximately 5 feet into a hole while excavating an area for construction of the aforementioned townhouse complex at Crofton Commons. Puzzled by what effect this collapse might have on this project, Carl A. Fischer, the project supervisor, had his equipment operators excavate the cave-in area.³ They discovered two dome-shaped chambers with radiating tunnels. For safety concerns, they back-filled the twenty-foot excavation wall. Boris Lang, Executive Vice President of Siedel Development, Inc., told his son Laurence “Larry” R. Lang about the cave-in. Larry and his friend Mark Kucher attempted to reopen the chambers the next day by hand digging. The following day Larry returned with another friend, Eric Dennard, an artist and instructor at Key School, Annapolis. By July 15 they had uncovered the first tunnel based on a description of the tunnel location given by Fischer. The Chesapeake Center for Environmental Studies, Smithsonian Institution, was contacted for professional assistance. The Center contacted Bastian who agreed to send someone to investigate the tunnel complex.

From Bastian’s request, Thomas Mayr, local amateur archeologists, and friends of Doepkens visited the tunnel complex on July 16 and offered technical assistance. On July 17, John Glaser, geologist and Barry McMullan, hydrographic engineer, Maryland Geological Survey, visited the locality at Bastian’s request and determined the tunnels were not of geological origin (Bastian, 1973:2). On July 18 Bastian, Paul Cresthull, an amateur archeologist who lived in the Crofton area, and Mayr, investigated the complex. Cresthull crawled part-way into one of the tunnels with a flashlight where at the end of it he discovered

“double incisor type grooves.”⁴ At this point, only one tunnel had been found. Bastian suggested they explore by cross-sectioning the tunnel and consult with someone familiar with animal burrows.

On July 19, Lang assisted the effort by providing a backhoe from the Siedel Corporation. Two more tunnels were uncovered and partially explored by physically crawling partially into them. Dennard contacted Dr. Clayton Ray, Department of Paleobiology, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, who said he would try to visit the tunnel complex. Dennard camped overnight next to the tunnel complex to protect it from “treasure hunters, tourists and vandals attracted by publicity” (Beard, 1973b:8). Larry Lang also “stood guard” at night to protect the complex (Anonymous, 1973a:3-C). By this time William P. Doepkens, a local farmer, naturalist, and amateur archeologist became interested in the tunnels. This leads to a long list of individuals who visited the locality to assist and offer their opinions as to the origin of the tunnels.

³ The following summary of the history of the tunnel complex investigation is taken from Bastian (1973) and Doepkens (1979a; 1979b). See these reports for a more detailed day by day narrative.

⁴ Wayne Clark email to Eshelman, December 19, 2007. Clark interviewed and recorded Mayr’s remembrance of the tunnels.

Figure 2. Eric Dennard peering from one of the tunnels. Washington *Star-News* July 25, 1973, photo by Francis Routt

On July 20, not hearing anything from Dr. Ray and knowing the contractors would only delay construction if the Smithsonian Institution or some other scientific institution “declared the site of importance” (Doepkens, 1979a:4; 1979b), Doepkens contacted Ivor Noël Hume, Department of Archeology, Colonial Williamsburg, who suggested he contact Garry Wheeler Stone, archeologist, St. Mary’s City Commission. Stone agreed to visit the tunnel complex the next day. With construction scheduled to begin at 1 pm that afternoon, Lang was able to persuade his father to delay work at the complex so that the archeologists from the St. Mary’s City Commission could investigate the tunnels the following day. Meanwhile, Lang, Dennard, and Doepkens carefully examined the newly opened tunnel walls and found 5/8 inch (1.6 cm) wide markings with a center ridge...consistent throughout the tunnels” (Doepkens, 1979:4).

On July 21 John Chaney, a local farmer, and plumbing contractor, brought in his backhoe and removed the spoil so the tunnel complex would be exposed and ready for the St. Mary’s City Commission team’s visit. To their word, Stone, Carson, Arthur C. Townsend, Executive Secretary of the Maryland Historical Trust, and several interns,⁵ visited the complex on July 21 and excavated and mapped the tunnel complex. They discovered a small complex of tunnels and chambers about 140 ft (43.7 m) west which had previously been partially exposed by Fischer and backfilled. By the end of the day, the team photographed and measured the exposed tunnels and rooms (see Figure 5). Of particular note, they reported that “some of the marks revealed one of the tools was worn or nicked on the working edge which left a very distinctive and repeated pattern of striations” (Bastian, 1973:4).

Initially, Carson is quoted as saying the tunnels were “a mysterious mining operation by pre-historic or colonial people” but he would need more time to make an exact judgment. Nevertheless, he was sure

the tunnels were man-made and were “some sort of mining endeavor” (Beard, 1973a:1). Lois Carr, historian for the St. Mary’s City Commission, thought that the fine clayey sand could be a type of “Fuller’s earth,” which was used in fulling or whitening cloth (Bastian, 1973:7). Doepkens (1979:5, Figure 20) discovered that there was a fulling mill in the 1760s at Good Intent, near the head of the South Branch of the South River about four miles (6.4 km) east of the tunnel complex.⁶

While the St. Mary’s City Commission team believed the marks were human-made, they believed the marks “were not of Colonial origin, but that they were probably dug by Indians, perhaps in a mining operation” (Bastian, 1973:4). Stone thought the slanting cuts were “made by Indians using a digging stick or bone, and that the broad marks with identical center ridges were made by a nicked tool or broad incisors (Doepkens, 1979:5).

When Bastian contacted Stone later that night Stone had softened his interpretation and thought that the marks “could be either Indian or animal...the marks had a break or crease in the middle and he thought that it could have been produced either by a tool or by a pair of incisors of a large animal” (Bastian, 1973:4). Stone described the marks as being 2 inches (5.08 cm) wide (Bastian 1973:4). Stone called Doepkens later that evening informing him that he had contacted Robert L. Humphrey, Jr., Chairman of the Department of Anthropology and a Specialist of Arctic Archeology at George Washington University and that he and George Stuart, Specialist in Middle American Archeology, National Geographic Society, Washington, D.C., would visit the tunnel complex the first of the week.

On July 22 Doepkens and others probed the small tunnels and found some of the tunnels had rather sharp turns. With further consideration given to the consistency of the markings throughout the chambers

⁵ Jonathan Kent, John Sands, and Joel Klein.

⁶ The fulling mill was offered for sale, at Public Vendue, by John Ducker in the *Maryland Gazette*, July 6, 1769.

and tunnels, Doepkens now believed beavers were responsible for digging the tunnels with their claws and teeth. Doepkens was also aware that the stream adjacent to the locality was called Beaver Dam Branch (Doepkens, 1979:5-6).

Getting desperate because of the anticipated startup of construction at the tunnel complex site, Bastian called Clifford Evans, Chairman of the Department of Anthropology, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, at his home. Based on a description of the tunnel complex by Bastian, Evans speculated the tunnels might have been dug by recently extinct Pleistocene glyptodonts or sloths (Bastian, 1973:4). Stone, after first believing the tunnels might have been the result of mining, agreed that based on the size and orientation of the marks on the tunnel walls, they were more likely that of an animal (Bastian, 1973:4). Bastian then called Dr. Ray who “could not think of any geologically recent animal in the Maryland area that would dig rooms and tunnels of the size and extent I described” (Bastian, 1973:5). Ray agreed to try to visit the complex the “following day [Monday] if time permitted.”

Early Monday morning Bastian received a “desperate call from Dennard who reported he could no longer hold off the contractor and that the tunnels would be destroyed the next day unless a scientist affiliated with a reputable institution would declare the tunnels to be of scientific importance” (Bastian, 1973:5). Bastian reported he had called Dr. Ray and he expected him to visit the tunnel complex that day. Despite the number of scientists who expressed opinions on the origin of the tunnel complex, many of whom also visited the locality, Doepkens was frustrated with the lack of attention given to the tunnel complex, especially by the Smithsonian Institution. Therefore, Doepkens notified the office of the Maryland 4th District Congressional Representative Marjorie S. Holt. Mike Owen of her office contacted Bastian who summarized

the efforts to date and Congresswoman Holt seemed to be satisfied that appropriate actions had been and were being taken (Bastian, 1973:5-6).

On July 24, Humphrey, Jr., and Stuart visited the tunnel complex and concluded that the tunnels were probably dug by beavers (Bastian, 1973:9). James R. Goldsberry, Maryland Wildlife Administration, had also visited the complex the same day and after doing some research he became convinced that the tunnels were wolf dens. Cresthull called Bastian stating that he had visited the locality and concluded the tunnels were made by wolves (see discussion below of wolf dens under Verdict: Who Made the Tunnel Complex?). It is unknown if Goldsberry and Cresthull had independently come to this same conclusion, but it is likely.⁷ Dr. Charles O. Handley, Department of Mammalogy, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution (based only on a phone call description given to him by Bastian) indicated “he did not know of any animal which would make such large and extensive tunnels” (Bastian, 1973:8).

Since both Drs. Ray and Handley doubted that animals had made the tunnels, Bastian decided to revisit the complex. Bastian called and asked Mayr to meet him at the complex. Dennard, Lang, and Doepkens were also present when Bastian arrived. Bastian (1973:7) recorded his observations of the tunnels and rooms. He states, “I concluded that the small diameter of the tunnels, the absence of artifacts, the consistently near-vertical orientation of the digging marks, the lack of indications of any material for which mining by tunneling would have been practical, and the lack of debris in the tunnels made it extremely unlikely that the tunnels were made by men (or children). The vertically undulating pattern of the tunnels and the lack of any apparent erosion from water seemed to make underground water an unlikely explanation. I was now thoroughly convinced that the problem should be investigated from a zoological or paleontological viewpoint.”

⁷ Cresthull cited L. David Mech, 1970, *The Wolf: The Ecology and Behavior of an Endangered Species*, Natural History Press, 384 pp.

The tunnel complex was backfilled by the contractors on the afternoon of July 25, 1973 (Bastian, 1973:10; Beard, 1973c; Anonymous, 1973a:C-3). Beard (1973c) reported that casts of the tooth marks, as well as sediment core samples, were taken by Lang, Dennard, and Doepkens and “will be studied with the assistance of Johns Hopkins University.”⁸

On August 2, Drs. Ray and Hotton visited the tunnel complex. “Dr. Hotton was convinced it [tunnels and chambers] was a natural formation until he got down on his back ... [and saw] the teeth and claw marks...About that time, the foreman got a machine [backhoe] and opened up a trench...it so happened they got into our old chamber and tunnels by mistake and opened some we hadn’t seen...amazed at the network of tunnels and chambers...went to a telephone to try and get some mammalogist out but was too late in the day” (Doepkens, 1979:10).

On August 3, Dr. Ray accompanied by Dr. Richard Thorington, Jr., mammalogist at the National Museum of Natural History, visited the tunnel complex. Bastian, in his field notes dated August 16, 1973, notes that Drs. Ray and Thorington “think beaver.” Ray and Thorington brought with them a skull of a giant beaver and a skin (“pelt”) with claws attached of the North American beaver to compare them with a tooth mark cast from the locality (Doepkens, 1979:10). Their conclusion was that the tunnel complex was made by the North American beaver (Anonymous, 1973b; Anonymous, 1973c).

COMPETING THEORIES

There are at least nine newspaper accounts from five different newspapers that did articles on the tunnel complex. The first published article was on the front page of the Annapolis *Evening Capital*, July 24, 1973, and entitled “Caverns in Crofton: Mysterious dig puzzles scientists.” The article cites Cary Carson, stating “the tunnels were clearly man-made because of the ax marks present” (Beard, 1973a:1). Carson speculated the grayish clay substance in the tunnels could be “Fuller’s earth” once used in the production

of cloth in the Colonial period. In the same article Dr. Hotton, apparently based on a phone conversation, is quoted as saying the tunnels are “probably a natural cave and could not have been dug by a prehistoric animal” but he added if it was not a natural cave produced by running water, “it could be an iron mine dug in colonial times” (Beard, 1973a:1). Apparently, Hotton did not realize the tunnel complex was located in unconsolidated Coastal Plain sediments, not the hard rock Piedmont Province, causing the writer to use the inaccurate term “Caverns.” Dr. Humphrey, Jr., was also apparently contacted by phone and is quoted as saying, he “agrees with Tyler Bastian, state archeologist, that it was probably made by an animal, but without the help of an animal paleontologist or mammalogist it will be difficult to distinguish the type of animal” (Beard, 1973a:8).

The next day, July 25, there were four articles from four different newspapers. Beard (1973b:1) reported that Humphrey, Jr., and Stuart had visited the tunnel complex and are quoted as stating “the caverns were probably the work of a prehistoric rodent of either the Pleistocene or later era.” The reporter goes on to say Humphrey and Stuart believed the “caverns and tunnels” are too small to be dug by man. They were probably dug by teeth or claw because there are no signs of metal tools. Beard adds “Smithsonian scientists have declined to visit the site, claiming they are too busy working on other projects.”

Sherwood (1973:1) in a photo caption states “...found no trace of ‘Crofton Man.’” Sherwood also states local farmer and amateur archeologist William Doepkens, speculates that the tunnels “looked more like a habitat for some kind of prehistoric rodent” and noted what appeared to be “buckteeth and claw marks on the side of one cave.” He noted that Dennard was making plaster casts of the “scratching on one wall.” Sherwood then repeats the same opinion of Dr. Hotton that Beard had made the day before, claiming the tunnels, “appear to have been caused by underground water

⁸ No results of these studies have been found and it is possible they were never undertaken.

seeping through this sand and clay mixture of [to] form these tunnels." Sherwood ends his article with

"Scratch one prehistoric Croton Man, Likewise, rodent. Enter parking lot."

Rousmaniere (1973:C28) noted that a "George Washington University expert" (Robert L. Humphrey, Jr.) opined that "large Pleistocene rodents" made the tunnels based on 'teeth-marks' on the sides of one of the caverns." Also, no artifacts or fossils had been found. Dr. Humphrey and Mr. Stuart ruled out the presence of man once they saw the tooth marks. They suggested "that large beavers" had made the tunnels "at least 1,000 years ago, but neither was positive." Again, the report was critical of the Smithsonian Institution, "which had declined to even visit the site."

Williams (1973:1) reported that Dr. Humphrey and Mr. Stuart thought the tunnels "might be the work of large, possibly prehistoric beavers, but that there was no sign of human activity there. Stuart is reported to have said, "That's a perfect beaver tooth," when shown one of the tooth marks in a den. Stuart and Humphrey, furthermore, said 'the animals which made the tunnels were larger than today's beavers because of the size of the tunnels...but cautioned that they are not experts in the field of prehistoric animals and only an experienced paleontologist could be certain of animals which dug the tunnels.' The article also mentions plaster casts were made of the "toothmarks."

An anonymous newspaper article (1973a:3-C) reported that "After three weeks of comments, observations from both amateur and professional archeologists, resentment from everyone that the Smithsonian Institution declined to send trained observers, and opinions from hundreds of people drawn to the site, the caves were leveled Wednesday afternoon (July 25, 1973)." The article states that "everyone agreed that if the Smithsonian people didn't come by noon they would have to level it." The superintendent for the developer, Fischer, stated, "As of 4:30 p.m. I can say that the dangerous excavations

have been leveled." Fischer continued, "The consensus was that they were burrows of a water-oriented animal which came from the nearby marshes and built caves in prehistoric times into the hillside...It's been three weeks...Everyone's satisfied that is the answer." Cresthull is reported to have claimed the marks on the tunnel and den walls were "probably claw marks from years ago."

Beard (1973c) reported on the same day as the bulldozing of the tunnel complex, that, "Speculation about the origin of the tunnels and cave have varied from a prehistoric or colonial mine to the den of giant beavers from the prehistoric Pleistocene era."

On August 3, Drs. Ray and Thorington visited the tunnel complex. Two anonymous newspaper articles (1973b, c) recorded the results of Drs. Ray and Thorington's visit. The Baltimore *Morning Sun* (1973b) reported that the tooth marks were made by the common beaver, not giant beavers. "It was the common beaver, not some large, prehistoric rodent, that dug the intriguing networks of tunnels." The tunnels lead to the banks of a stream called Beaver Dam Creek. The Baltimore *Evening Sun* (1973c) reported scientists from the National Museum of Natural History "have knocked down a theory that a network of tunnels found...in Crofton... were dug by some sort of prehistoric rodents. Common beavers did the digging..."

In *Weird America*, a guidebook to places of mystery in the United States, Brandon (1978) states "An area being made into a parking lot in July of 1973 was found to be infested with small tunnels, about 20 inches wide. Some persons crawled into them and found them more extensive than they cared--or dared--to explore. There was conjecture that they may have been produced by some prehistoric miniman. But William Doepkens, an amateur archeologist, found reason for believing that the array was the habitat of some unknown giant rodent since he saw large tooth and claw marks on the side of one cave. No rodent remains of any kind, however, were found." Finally, Frizzell (2005) repeats the same story online but adds photos of what the locality looks like today.

This is the last mention of the Crofton Tunnel Complex until a footnote mentions it in a paleontological paper published by Eshelman et al. (2018:11 n1).⁹

It is unclear how many interviews for radio and live broadcasts may have been conducted during the investigation of the tunnel complex.

TUNNEL COMPLEX DESCRIPTION

Doepkens (1979a) used a series of letters and numbers to identify the different chambers and tunnels. Thus, C1 is chamber 1 etc. and T1 is tunnel one, etc. A total of ten chambers and twenty tunnels were identified during the excavations. This averages out to two tunnels per chamber. Some chambers had only one tunnel while C1-C2 had potentially as many as five or even six tunnels. How many more chambers and tunnels were present in this complex is unknown? The number of chambers and tunnels suggest either there was at one time a large number of beavers living together and/or these diggings represent building of dens and tunnels over an extended period of time. The Alaska Department of Fish & Game states that bank beavers (discussed below) may have several tunnel entrances with at least one above the high-water mark and another below the low water mark (Golden, 2008).

The St. Mary's City Commission sketch map (see Figure 5) also provides measurements of chambers and tunnels. They show one tunnel at least 3.4 m (11 ft) long, two at least 3.0 m (10 ft) long and one at least 2.3 m (7.5 ft) long. Doepkens (1979: 17) described T2 as, "To the right, it went four feet [1.22 m] to a dead end. To the left, it went upgrade about 10 feet [3.05 m] and then branched into a Y."

Doepkens (1979:17) described T3 as "dipped slightly downward before slanting upward eight feet or more." The guidebook *Muskrat and Beaver Management in Wetlands* (2004) report dens connected by tunnels six to fifty feet back in the bank above the water level.

One of the first persons to describe the tunnel complex was Eric Dennard who stated it was comprised of "two bee-hive-shaped rooms 9 [2.75 m] to 12 ft [3.66 m] in diameter and 9 ft [2.74 m] high. The rooms were about 2 ft [0.61 m] apart and were connected by a tunnel 2 ft [0.61 m] in diameter...There was at least one additional tunnel leading off from the room in which the bulldozer fell. The later room also had a vertical vent hole leading to the ground surface" (Bastian, 1973:2). Garry Stone described the complex "as a hole blossoming into a 20-foot cavern¹⁰ with mine shafts that radiated 15 to 20 feet into the hillside before stopping (Beard, 1973:1). Bastian (1973:3) described the tunnels during his first visit on July 18 stating, "The tunnel appeared to be about 2 ft [0.61 m] in diameter, undulated vertically, and about 6 feet [1.83 m] from the entrance it branched rather abruptly to the right and left." Bastian reported that Dennard found the right branch dead-ended but the left branch "continued for an undetermined distance." Dennard noted that "A black substance which disintegrated upon contact" was observed on the walls of one of these branches but it was not collected. A black substance is also noted in a detailed slide of the tooth marks. Bastian (1973:7)¹¹ described the tunnel complex as follows on his second visit on July 23, "Original dome now well-cleared; ca. 9-10 ft [2.75-3.95 m] in dia and 3 [0.91 m] or 4 ft [1.22 m] high with a collapsed roof. Tunnels 13-16 in [0.33-0.41 m], in dia with rarely over 18 in [0.46 m]."

⁹ The initial title of Doepkens' 1979a paper describes the beaver as "extinct." After the printing of this first report, perhaps initiated by comments, Doepkens reinterpreted the tunnel complex as dug by the North American beaver.

¹⁰ It is unfortunate the term cave or cavern was used by Stone and Hotton to describe the chambers and tunnels because they are neither. These terms were then used by newspaper reporters which caused widespread misrepresentation as to what these chamber dens and tunnels actually were.

¹¹ In addition to Bastian's Narrative Report, his field notes are also located at the Maryland Historical Trust library. These include the names of all the persons he contacted during this investigation.

These measurements are similar to known dimensions of beaver lodges. Morgan (1868:141) provides exterior water level dimensions of a beaver lodge in upper Michigan as 16.4 feet (4.8 m) by 19.9 feet (6.1 m) and height of 4.6 feet (1.4 m) and the interior chamber dimension of 7.8 feet (2.4m) by 7 (2.1 m) and height of 1.4 feet (0.4 m). Morgan (1868:148) also gives exterior water level dimensions of a bank lodge (discussed below) as 12 feet (3.7 m) by 14 feet (4.3 m) and height on the landside 3.5 feet (1.1 m), height on the riverside 6.5 feet (2.0 m), interior chamber dimension of 6 feet (1.8 m) and height of chamber from floor of lodge 2.5 feet (0.8 m). Golden (2008) notes den size average for some Alaska beavers are somewhat smaller at 2 feet wide (0.61 m) by 3 feet (0.91m) long by 3 feet (0.91 m) high.

Doepkens (1979a:17-20, Figures 14-17), provides descriptions of seven “excavations” made during the investigation of the complex including the approximate diameter of rooms and length, width, and height of tunnels. This detailed information is not presented here but the more interesting observations are discussed. Figures 14 & 15 from Doepkens (1979a:22), Diagrams 1, 2 and 3 from Doepkens et al. (1979:12-14), as well as, the measured drawing of the tunnel complex executed by the St. Mary’s City Commission (see Figure 5 below) are included in this report. Doepkens (1979a:17) states the largest chamber, C1, measured 11 (3.35 m) by 15 feet (4.6 m) and had a maximum height of 4 feet (1.22 m). The map view in Doepkens (1979a:21) reproduced below as Figure 3, shows two chambers side by side. But the discussion of “Excavation 1” states Fischer noted there was a “short tunnel” through a two-foot wall (0.61 m) that connected the two chambers (C1 and C2). The St. Mary’s City Commission drawing was done after the roof of C2 had partially collapsed and the wall between the two chambers had been destroyed. Their measurement shows the greatest width of 14.9 feet (4.54 m) and length of the now combined two chambers as 23.8 feet (7.25 m). This would suggest the two chambers were approximately 11 (3.35 m) to 13 (3.96 m) feet each. Note in Figure 6 there are hatched

lines that represent “Fischer’s Version” of the dens C1 and C2. Fischer, the project supervisor, was present when the two chambers were first discovered.

Note that Doepkens measurements are rounded to the nearest foot or in some case to the nearest half foot. The St. Mary’s City Commission measurements are given to the nearest 1/10 of a foot. Thus, some of the chamber measurements are possibly reported somewhat larger than they really were. C1, the largest chamber, had a maximum height of only four feet (1.22 m). Bastian (1979:7) states, “Original dome now well-cleared; ca. 9-10 ft (2.74-3.05 m) in dia and 3 or 4 ft (0.91-1.22 m) high with collapsed roof. Tunnels 13-16 in. (33.0-40.6 cm) in dia with rarely over 18 in. (45.7 cm).” In parentheses, he added, “The diameter of the room was actually somewhat larger.” Presumably Bastian was referring to C1, but still, his ca. 9-10 foot (2.74-3.05 m) diameter, even if it was “somewhat larger,” is probably less than the measurements given by Doepkens who concluded the dimensions to be 11 feet (3.35 m) by 15 feet (3.96 m). Doepkens measurements, at least in this case, are probably overestimates.

Doepkens describes most of the tunnels as being relatively straight but a few having sharp turns. Morgan (1868:144) notes that the entrances to a beaver lodge usually consist of two tunnels but other entrances may be added with up to three or four total entrances. These entrances are of two kinds. One is straight, or as nearly so as possible, with its floor, which begins underwater with an inclined plane rising gradually above the water level into the chamber. The second type has an abrupt incline and often sinuous in its course. The first tunnel type he called the “wood entrance,” is designed to facilitate the admission into the chamber of the beaver’s “wood cuttings, while the second tunnel type is called the “beaver entrance,” which is usually abrupt and often winding (Morgan, 1868:144).

Bennett (1835:320-321) notes that in the 1829 *Transactions of the Berlin Natural History Society*, is an 1822 account that records fifteen to twenty beavers (European beaver *Castor fiber*) which had occupied a

colony for upwards of a century on a little river near its confluence with the Elbe in the district of Magdeburg. The beavers dug burrows of thirty or forty paces in length, on a level with the stream, with one opening below the surface of the water, and another upon the land. Bennett states, "All their habits indeed, as here described, coincide so exactly with those of the American beavers." Assuming a normal walking step of ~ 0.75 m (0.82 yd)¹² this equates to tunnel lengths of 22.5 m (74 ft) to 30 m (98 ft). Even if these dimensions are exaggerated two-fold, tunnel lengths of 11.2 m (37 ft) to 14.9 m (49 ft) are impressive.

Hearne (1795:244), referring to beavers in Hudson Bay area states it, "has been so repeatedly reported of these animals [beavers] assembling in great bodies, and jointly erecting large towns, cities, and commonwealths, as they have sometimes been called, I am confident from many circumstances, that even where the greatest number of beaver are situated in the neighborhood of each other, their labors are not carried on jointly in the erection of their different habitations." A colony consists of one or more families. The number of individual animals per colony varies from 1 to 12 or more, depending upon conditions (Muskrat and Beaver Management in Wetlands, 2004).

Figure 3. Map view of Crofton Tunnel Complex ("Crofton Beaver Site") showing topography and stadia locations, Doepkens (1979a:21 Figure 14) report. "BASELINE" apparently is a survey boundary used by Doepkens' team.

¹² [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pace_\(unit\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pace_(unit))

It is also interesting to compare the drawings of the tunnels and chambers on Doepken's plan map in relation to the "swamp" which he likewise records. Presumably, this was either part of Beaver Dam Creek and/or a pond as a result of beaver dam construction. Figure 8 shows all the tunnels dipping downward, not constructed horizontally. The figure shows the lower end of seven tunnels are clearly below the level of the "swamp." Doepkens (1979a:15, Figure 8) states T6 "probably was an entrance to the swamp" and T7 "leads toward the swamp." Actually, these are underwater entrances used

by beavers to safely gain access to their dens and living areas.

Stone (1973:2) and Doepkens (1979a:13, Figure 6 caption) note that marks on the sides of some tunnels disappear near the floor as if they were eroded by water. Doepkens states, "T1 half full of silt. Sides below silt level were very smooth and worn as were all sides of tunnels below water level." While water erosion is possible it is more likely the marks may have been rubbed out by the dragging of branches into the tunnels for food and bedding.

Figure 4. Diagram 1 from Doepkens et al. 1979 report showing topography and approximate layout of the tunnel and den complex.

Figure 6. Detail map view of the Chambers 1 and 2 areas of the Crofton Tunnel Complex from Doepkens (1979a:21, Figure 15) report. Note the hatched line represents "Fischer's Version" of the dens area who initially excavated the locality.

side view is an estimate (close but not precise).
 picture plane tilted to show all
 excavations

Diagram 2

Figure 8. Diagram 2 from Doepkens et al. 1979 report showing the approximate cross-section layout of the tunnel and den complex. Note many of the lower tunnel entrances are below the swamp level.

Figure 9. Map views of chambers 4 and 6 and cross-section layout of chambers and tunnels from Doepkens (1979a:22, Figures 16, 17, 18, 19) report.

Photographs of the tunnels were made by Doepkens, Bastian, and the St. Mary's City Commission field team. The Bastian slides are located at the Maryland Historical Trust library. The St. Mary's City Commission slides are located at Historic St. Mary's City, Department of Archeology. Doepkens' slides were never seen. His son, William, thought the slides might be stored away but after repeated reminders, they were never made available. Doepkens mentioned a box of his best slides were mixed up by the photo developing company, someone else getting his slides by mistake. Thus the only Doepkens images available are poor copies reproduced in Doepkens (1979a) and Doepkens et al. (1979) reports. The best images are

those deposited at the Maryland Historical Trust library.

AGE OF TUNNEL COMPLEX

No contemporary organic material such as bone or plant remains was reported by the investigators of the tunnels except for a black coating covering some of the walls. The coating may have been mold. Beavers use rooms within tunnel complexes to store food¹³ and as resting and living areas typically covered with vegetative bedding material. The absence of such organic material suggests either it had completely decayed over time or the tunnels or dens never had such materials. The latter seems highly unlikely suggesting the complex was not active in recent

¹³ Beavers defecate in the water, not in their den, Living with Wildlife: Beavers, 2018, <https://wdfw.wa.gov/living/beavers.html>

years. Den roof collapse is not uncommon. A roof collapse could have provided an opportunity for organic preservation, but none is reported by Bastian (1973), Doepkens (1979a; 1979b), or Doepkens et al. (1979). This suggests that either no collapses were identified, the fine sandy matrix did not seal the organic material effectively for preservation, or no vegetative material was present. Dennard did take two samples of soil from the complex which the Maryland Geological Survey studied. They found no evidence of organic matter or pollen for palynology study suggesting that any organic matter if present had been leached out.

Doepkens (1979a:15, 17, Figures 4 and 10) reports “dark soil” was detected on the floor of C1 and C6. One soil sample was taken from Ex1-C1-T4 (excavation 1, chamber 1, tunnel 4). It is unclear but it appears this was one of the soil samples collected and examined by John D. Glaser of the Maryland Geological Survey.¹⁴ In his report Glaser refers to a “spot sample” reportedly collected from the walls and floors of one of the tunnels which were found to be contaminated with modern organic residues including sprouting seeds. He determined a palynology analysis would not be meaningful. Doepkens (1979a:19) reports that “Samples of hickory nuts, acorns, and other seeds taken” from the floor of T16 but they “appear to have floated in with water when the tunnel opened.” Stone (1973:2) states “A sample of seeds was recovered from the spring at the mouth of tunnel no. 5, but these appeared to have been washing in from the modern ground level.” Tunnel no. 5 (see Figure 5), appears to be the same as T1 (see Figures 6 and 9). Glaser did not state it in his report, but no organic material was recovered that was suitable for a C14 date.

Beaver was commercially trapped out in the coastal plain of the Mid-Atlantic region by about 1700 if not earlier. There were never large numbers of beaver in

Southern Maryland at the time of English settlement, and serious fur trading had already been underway for 15 to 20 years. Lord Baltimore hoped to reap a quick return on his huge gamble through furs but local supplies were already slender. The Crofton complex of tunnels would imply either a substantial population and/or a long period of use in the area by beavers.¹⁵

The heaviest trapping of beaver in Ohio occurred between 1750 and 1800. In the 1770s, David Zeisberger, a Moravian Missionary remarked, “The beaver was formerly found in great numbers in this region, but since the Indians have learned from the whites to catch them in steel-trap [steel-trap], they are more rarely found.” Because of intense trapping, beaver populations drastically fell and by the end of the 18th century, the beaver was extirpated from Ohio (American Beaver, 2018). Morgan (1868:32) states that by 1830, beaver had “substantially disappeared from the United States east of the Rocky Mountains, except in the States of Michigan, Wisconsin, Minnesota, and Iowa; and in the Territories of Nebraska, Dakota, Idaho, Montana, and Colorado. They are still occasionally seen in Maine, New York, and Virginia.”

By the early 1900s, beavers were almost extirpated from North America, Europe, and Asia due to trapping, subsequent draining of lands for agriculture and tree removal (About beavers, 2018). More recently the beaver has made a comeback, even becoming a pest in some regions because of their dam building and pond development that disrupts human usage of the same land areas (Sutor, 2010; Anonymous, 2014).

The earliest use of the place name “Beaver Dam Neck” is found in 1662 - Liber 5, Folio 624, describing it as at the head of Rhode River on Muddy Creek... to a beaver dam ...1669, Liber 13, Folio 13...to and bounding on Beaver Dam Branch near Annapolis. This is where Maryland Route 2 crosses Church Creek, and nearby the hill is known as Beaver Dam Hill. Also, on

¹⁴ Glaser’s one-page comments are attached to the end of Bastian’s 1973 narrative report of investigations.

¹⁵ Henry Miller email to Eshelman, September 19, 2018.

Middle Plantation (18AN46) patented in 1664, Liber 7, Folio 450 - 52, a beaver jaw was found sometime between 1670 and 1700 (Doepkens, 1979a:24).

Roads and Creeks in the area are named after beavers and their dams. Beaver Dam Road crosses Beaver Dam Creek, a tributary of the Northeast Branch of the Anacostia River, approximately 8.9 miles (14.2 km) west of the Crofton Tunnel Complex. Beaver Road, Hyattsville is approximately 12.5 miles (20.3 km) southwest of Crofton. Beaverkill¹⁶ Road, Columbia, is approximately 17.8 miles (28.7 km) northwest of Crofton. Beaver Court, Beaver Dam Road, Beaver Run Lane and, Beaver Brook Lane are all about 32 miles (52 km) north of Crofton.

Doepkens (1979a:4) reported that John Chaney, "had extensively walked and hunted the surrounding area which was formerly owned and farmed by his father and grandfather...recalled his father, Benjamin Franklin Chaney, telling him that in his youth, about 1890, he observed beaver in the Crofton Area." A beaver specimen in the National Museum of Natural History (NMNH 505339) was collected from Beaver Creek, Beck Branch, Prince George's County, Maryland, in 1973.

Doepkens (1979a:28) wrote that "Careful excavation of the floor of the main chamber and sub-chamber area yielded no evidence of any wood remains. Surely, if the complex had been abandoned within the last 100 years, something of this nature should have been uncovered. The manner in which the complex had been sealed off and preserved, in accordance with the absence of any organic remains, and the remarkable stability of the soil, suggests that the complex is 275 years old or older, and was dug by Maryland's native beaver." Without datable organic material, the Crofton Tunnel Complex probably dates from the Holocene Epoch, possibly during the early historic period.

DESCRIPTION OF INCISOR MARKS ON TUNNEL AND CHAMBER WALLS

Doepkens (1979a:11, Figure 2) when referring to Excavation 1, C1, states, "Note the distinguished tooth and claw marks. The identification of these markings held the key to determining the origin of the [tunnel] complex. We contacted many scientists in the animal field and although they said they saw no reason why beavers could not dig with their teeth, none had either any knowledge that beavers actually did use their teeth when digging burrows, or any knowledge that anyone who had examined a beaver burrow had ever described the method of digging that beavers employed."

Doepkens and the other investigators in 1973 did not have the advantage of the internet that investigators have today. In fact, there are reports of beavers using their teeth to assist in the digging of tunnels and dens, but claws are considered the primary digging tool employed.

Waterhouse (1848:2) states, "Sometimes the width of the incisor is very great, and exceeds the depth; the rodents which burrow, and live almost entirely under ground, present this form of incisors, their powerful teeth being, no doubt, used to gnaw through the roots which would otherwise obstruct their subterranean course. Those of the upper jaw are always shorter than those of the lower, and usually, describe about three parts of a circle. The larger incisors of the lower jaw form a smaller segment of a larger circle."

Doepkens (1979a:11) in the caption for Figure 3¹⁷ showing the wall of T10 (tunnel) notes "really clean tooth marks on the upper half of wall and also near total absence of claw marks." Doepkens (1979a:17), referring to T10 states "Tooth and claw marks very distinct." Bastian (1973:7) notes that "The majority of the marks are narrow and nearly V-shaped. All marks are nearly perpendicular to the floor of the chambers" Beavers primarily dig with their claws so it is not surprising that most of the marks on the chambers and tunnels are vertical "narrow" and "V-shaped" marks the result of claw digging.

¹⁶ Beaverkill may mean Beaver River as in the sense of Dutch.

¹⁷ No negative or original image of Figure 3 was obtained. The quality of the image in the report is too poor for inclusion in this paper.

Doepkens (1979a:19) states that for T15 the, “Sides, top, bottom and end were distinctly dug with teeth. No claw marks visible. On the sides and end, the teeth marks were vertical and on the top and bottom, the marks were horizontal. No sign of wear.” Doepkens (1979a:20) states that for T18, “Teeth and claw marks were vertical on the side and horizontal on the top and bottom and appeared to have been worn.”

Stone’s and Doepkens’ observations of the marks on the tunnel and chamber walls are interpreted as two lower or upper incisors, side by side, one from each side of either the mandibular symphysis of the lower jaw or the maxilla. Because of the slightly rounded anterior edge of the incisors, they would form a double incisor mark with a small ridge down the middle indicative of the small gap between the two incisors. This interpretation is supported by the marks shown in the photographs housed at the Maryland Historical Trust library. A slight ridge is seen on the marks.

The tooth marks shown in Figure 11 below appear to have been made by lower incisors. Movement of the lower incisors in an upward manner would create the plucking appearance of the surrounding matrix at the upper end of the tooth marks. Movement of upper molars in a downward motion would show a gentle increase in the depth of the cut, not an abrupt upper tooth mark edge as seen in the photos. Beavers are able to close their lips behind their incisors so they can feed underwater (Morgan, 1868:48; Trottier, 2003:2). This may also help keep chips from entering their mouth as well as dirt when digging.

INCISOR MARKS WIDTH MEASUREMENTS

Bastian (1973:7) referring to C1-C2 states,

Tool or tooth marks 5/8 in. [1.6 cm] wide with low center ridge – paired incisors? The majority of the marks are narrow and nearly V-shaped.

All marks are nearly perpendicular to the floor of dome and reportedly same in the tunnels.

Stone (1973) states,

...with careful troweling it was quite easy to flake the soft spoil from the walls of the features without damaging the original surface. [This was necessary because the original discovery was backfilled.] The impressions of the tool used to excavate the features were quite clear: parallel slanting cuts made by a digging stick, bone, or broad incisor. No ‘claw’ marks were visible. Many of the marks had identical central ridges as if left by a nicked tool.

From these descriptions, the slightly double rounded marks were made from beaver incisors approximately 1.6 cm wide and the narrow and V-shaped marks were made by beaver claws. No measurements are given by Bastian or Doepkens for the claw marks but by crude comparison based on photos and line drawing (see Figures 10 and 11) the claw mark widths are estimated to be about 1/4 or 1/5 the width of the incisor marks. Caliper measurements of claw marks on a cast (see Figure 12 below) from the Historic St. Mary’s City collection range from 4.78 to 6.03 mm in width. The incisor marks are interpreted to represent two lower incisors, side by side, one from each side of the mandibular symphysis. Because of the slightly rounded anterior edge of the incisors and a small gap between them, the paired incisors would form a double incisor mark with a small ridge down the middle. This interpretation is supported by the marks shown in the photographs from the Maryland Historical Trust and the cast from Historic St. Mary’s City where a slight ridge can be seen in the center of some of the marks.

Figure 10. Drawing of double incisor and claw marks on the wall of C1 used as cover page image of Doepkens (1979a) report. Note the use of the term “extinct” in the report title. On the Doepkens’ et al. (1979) report a drawing of the North American beaver is used as the cover page.

Figure 11. Tooth marks are visible in the upper half of the image. Note the black coating in the center and right portion of the image. Image by Tyler Bastian, July 23, 1973.

Figure 12. Tooth and claw marks on Historic St. Mary's City cast made July 20, 1973. Historic St. Mary's City photograph. The claw marks are the V-shaped narrow vertical scratches in the upper portion of the cast and the incisor marks are the wider smoother double gouges in the lower portion of the image.

Figure 13. Photo images of *Castoroides dilophidus*, a related giant beaver species restricted to Florida and coastal regions of Georgia and South Carolina, lower incisors showing enamel ridge groove patterns on the anterior face. Incisors of *C. ohioensis* have similar incisor enamel ridge patterns. No such enamel ridges were found on the tooth marks at Crofton Tunnel Complex. Source of image Hulbert et al. (2014:39, Figure 7). Image reproduced with permission of the Florida Museum of Natural History

FIGURE 14. Image of *Castoroides ohioensis* incisor illustrating the enamel ridges. Also note the tooth is peg-like in diameter, while a *Castor* incisor has a flatter anterior surface. Image from fossilera.com.

Beavers dig tunnels and canals largely with their claws. Claw marks are relatively common in many of the slides that were taken of the Crofton tunnels and chambers.¹⁸ There are however some areas where incisor marks are clearly visible. Stone described the marks as being 2 inches (5.08 cm) wide (Bastian 1973:4). Lang, Dennard, and Doepkens described the tooth marks as “5/8 in. [1.6 cm] wide” with “center ridge” which “were consistent throughout the tunnels” (Doepkens, 1979a:5). Bastian (1973:7) described the marks as, “Tool or tooth marks 5/8 in [1.6 cm] wide with low center ridge – paired incisors?” Bastian had correctly speculated that some of the marks were indeed animal incisor marks. Was Stone’s measurement for the width of double incisor marks, while Bastian was measuring the width of a single incisor tooth mark? This would help to explain the difference in measurement given by Stone as 5.08 cm as opposed to those given by Bastian and Doepkens as 1.6 cm. If both incisors were included plus the small gap between them, the approximate measurement

would be about 3.4 cm. Even if this assumption is correct, there is still a significant difference between 5.08 cm and 3.4 cm. Did Bastian misunderstand what Stone had said during their phone conversation? Did Bastian make a mistake in his narrative report? Did Stone mean 2 cm [0.79 inches], which would be approximately 5/8 of an inch for the width of a single incisor mark which is what was estimated based on the scaled photographic analysis discussed below?¹⁹ Measuring old concave tooth marks in a soft fine sandy clay (Doepkens, 1979a:5, 24) matrix is difficult due to the potential loss of matrix around the sharp edge of the tooth marks over time. Also, it is not clear what measuring instruments were used – rulers, calipers or estimation. Stone may have meant 2 cm, not 2 inches or Bastian wrote inches when he meant cm. A careful study of the tooth marks in the slides also suggested the beaver did not always dig perpendicular to the

¹⁸ Slides from the Crofton Tunnel Complex are located at Historic St. Mary’s City and Maryland Historical Trust library.

¹⁹ Nothing on this subject was found in Bastian’s notes retained at the Maryland Historical Trust library.

face of the wall but often deliberately approached the wall surface slightly from the side so either the right or left incisor dug farther into the wall than the other.

The tooth marks in Doepkens (1979a:11 Figures 2 and 3) report are not clear and the location of the original photographs are unknown. An attempt was made to determine measurements of the incisor marks from photographic slides that had been taken by Tyler Bastian in the tunnel complex and deposited at the Maryland Historical Trust. Bastian included a white and red scale that is marked as “5 cm” (see Figure 11). Using a simple relative comparison of the size of the scale on a photograph made from among the best slides showing these incisor marks (photographs by Tyler Bastian, July 23, 1973, Anne Arundel slide binder, Maryland Historical Trust library) with the 5 cm scale a determination of the relative width of three incisor marks was made. Based on this scale in the Bastian photograph, the width of the three best incisor marks range from 1.48 cm to 1.85 cm. These measurements compare well with Bastian’s (1973:7) measurement of 5/8 inch or 1.6 cm.²⁰

The estimated width of both incisors side by side in the jaw would be approximately 15 mm (1.5 cm) to 16 (1.6 cm) mm. Giant beaver (*Castoroides*) incisor widths for USNM 181574 (left mandible with incisor) and USNM 9035 (isolated left incisor) both measure 22 (2.2 cm) mm or 4.4 cm for a pair. The inner medial edge of the incisors are worn and taper toward the tip, but it is clear from the photos that the tooth marks are from the anterior cutting edge of the incisors. Giant beaver incisors have a ridge groove pattern on the outer enamel surface parallel to the length of the tooth (see Figure 13 above) while living beaver (*Castor*) incisors have a smooth outer enamel surface. The incisor marks observed in the slides show no evidence of

ridge groove pattern outer enamel scars. Assuming the “5/8 in. (1.6 cm) estimate of the paired incisor marks in the tunnel complex given by Bastian are correct, the tooth marks compare well with paired *Castor* incisors and are significantly smaller (1.7 cm versus 4.4 cm) than paired *Castoroides* incisors. In addition, the anterior face of *Castoroides* incisors is more rounded as the tooth is a curved peg-shaped while the *Castor* incisors are more flat and only slightly rounded on the outer enamel surface.

A more perfect way to measure the incisor marks would be from casts. Mention of casts of the incisor marks and where they were made in the tunnel complex are reported in Doepkens (1979a:8, 9, 10, 17, 18, 20, 27, 30). As best as be can determined at least one cast was given to Larry Lang,²¹ son of the owner of the company that built the Crofton townhouses. The whereabouts of that cast, if it was ever kept, is unknown.²² William Doepkens also reported he had a cast but his son has not been able to find it. After this paper was initially submitted for publication, Henry Miller of Historic St. Mary’s City notified the author he and his staff discovered a cast of the Crofton Tunnel Complex tooth and claw marks while sorting some collections.²³ One of the long lost casts had fortuitously been found. Using calipers three sets of paired incisors marks were measured. The widths ranged from 15.24 to 16.25 mm. In addition, the incisors of a skull of a North American beaver was fitted onto the cast incisor marks and the fit was nearly perfect. Everything matched. The measurements compare favorably in size and shape with incisor for *Castor canadensis* in Table 1 below.

Table 1 provides measurements of beaver (*Castor canadensis*) upper and lower incisors. The measurements include individual incisor widths at both the distal end and at the alveolus contact as well as the

²⁰ Matt McKnight and Dennis Curry, current or former staff at Maryland Historical Trust, confirm the scale increments are 5 cm each.

²¹ Meredith McQuoid-Greason email to Eshelman et al. November 16, 2018.

²² David Bohaska email to Eshelman et al., November 14, 2018.

²³ Henry Miller email to Eshelman, July 1, 2019.

overall width of both upper incisors measured together, and width of both lower incisors measured together. Because of damage in some specimens, measurements could not be obtained for some dimensions. The specimens measured came from Maryland (1 individual), Washington, D.C. (1 individual), Virginia (collected very near Washington, D.C.; 1 individual) and Pennsylvania (2 individuals). The Maryland specimen was collected in 1973 approximately 10 miles west of the Crofton Beaver Tunnel Complex.

The distal width of the upper incisors (4) range from 6.96 to 7.85 mm. The alveoli width of the upper incisors (4) range from 7.20 to 8.43 mm. The width of the left and right upper incisors (3) measured together at the distal tip range from 15.61 to 15.99 mm. The width of the left and right upper incisors (2) measured together at the alveolus range from 15.97

to 17.39 mm. The distal width of lower incisors (7) range from 7.12 to 8.10 mm. The alveoli width of the lower incisors (7) range from 7.01 to 8.64 mm. The width of the left and right lower incisors (3) measured together at the distal tip range from 14.38 to 15.70 mm. The width of a lower left and right lower incisor (1) measured together at the alveolus is 15.91 mm. By converting the measurements from mm to cm, the measurements from Table 1 compare well with the incisor marks found on the tunnel and chamber walls of the Crofton Tunnel Complex (i.e. a range of 1.48 to 1.85 cm from the tunnel complex and a range of 1.44 to 1.57 cm for the lower incisors distal width and 1.6 cm for lower incisor alveolus width. These measurements are well outside the comparable measurement for *Castoroides*.

Catalog No.	left upper distal width	right upper distal width	left upper alveolus width	right upper alveolus width	left and right upper distal width	left and right upper alveolus width	left lower distal width	right lower distal width	left lower alveolus width	right lower alveolus width	left and right lower distal width	left and right lower alveolus width
USNM 060365 ²⁴	7.85	7.66	x	x	15.97	15.97	7.69	7.46	x	x	15.01	x
USNM 246536 ²⁵	x	x	x	x	x	x	8.10	8.09	8.64	7.80	15.70	x
USNM 246543 ²⁶	6.96	7.42	7.20	8.43	15.61	x	7.97	7.50	7.99	7.50	14.38	x
USNM 505339 ²⁷	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	7.12	x	7.02	x	x
USNM 570156 ²⁸	x	x	7.54	7.86	15.99	17.39	x	x	7.01	6.77	x	15.91

Table 1. Distal and alveolus width measurements for *Castor canadensis* individual upper and lower incisors and paired widths of upper and lower incisors.

²⁴ Four Mile Run, Virginia, collected 1894.

²⁵ Union County, Pennsylvania, collected 1926.

²⁶ Conrad, Potter County, Pennsylvania, collected 1926.

²⁷ Beaver Cree, Beck Branch, Prince George's County, Maryland, collected 1973.

²⁸ Washington, D.C., collection date unknown.

The lengths and widths of individual teeth of *Caster* show a pattern of exponential growth in nearly a linear increase in size within the first four years of age with only little size increase with age thereafter reaching a nearly constant size from about the age of 6–7 years, and absolute maximum around an age of about 10 years (Stefen, 2009). Most if not all of the variation in incisor size found in Table 1 above can be explained by age and individual differences.

Suspects: The Habits and Habitats of North American Beaver, extinct Giant Beaver, Mountain Beaver and Wolves

North American Beaver: Kurtén and Anderson (1980:238) state “In northern and montane areas, beavers build elaborate lodges with underwater chambers out of mud and stick; in the Southwest and Midwest, they dig burrows in the banks of streams and lakes.” There are two errors in this statement. The chambers are not underwater but the entrance tunnels usually are underwater. Also, bank burrows are known to be built by beavers throughout their range. On the Eastern Shore of Maryland and in Coastal Plain of Virginia, there are known occurrences of beavers that build bank tunnels along streams and edges of ponds created by the beaver from dam building.²⁹

Bank dens have been observed in Alabama that were converted to lodges as the water level in ponds increased over time. Bank dens are not used in some area, such as Newfoundland where rocky conditions and permafrost in other regions many preclude bank den construction (Hill, 1982:264). Wilsson (1971) notes that feeding chambers are often located near the water within the main tunnel leading to resting or sleeping areas off bank dens.

Morgan (1868:139-140) states,

A characteristic of the beaver is that he is a burrowing animal with an indulging propensity to excavate chambers underground, and construct artificial lodges upon its surface, both of which are indispensable to his security and happiness...There are reasons for believing that the burrow is the normal residence of the beaver; and that the lodge grew out of it.

Morgan (1868:83) also states,

As the dam is not an absolute necessity to the beaver for the maintenance of his life, his normal habitation being rather natural ponds and rivers, and burrows in their banks, it is, in itself considered, a remarkable fact that he should have voluntarily transferred himself, by means of dams and ponds of his own construction, from a natural to an artificial mode of life.

The Merriam-Webster dictionary defines “bank beaver” as “a beaver that inhabits burrows in stream banks instead of making a house and dam.”³⁰ Lisle (2010) states, “

Digging in banks is...to make...dens as protection from predators and the elements...tunnels and burrows...are usually isolated from one another, simple, and shallow. A typical tunnel is just wide enough to accommodate beavers and begins immediately below the water's surface, angling upwards into a bank where it ends in a living chamber. The increase in elevation helps ensure that the den stays dry during high-water events. Most tunnels are relatively short.

However, Link (2004) states,

²⁹ Darrin Lowery communication to Eshelman November 9, 2018. Lowery recalls seeing a beaver emerge from one of these burrows near Trapp, Talbot County, Maryland. The burrow was about six inches above the water level of the pond. Lowery claims other “bank beavers” have been reported from near the headwaters of Tuckahoe Creek, a tributary of the Choptank River, Talbot County,

Maryland. Wayne Clark oral communication to Eshelman January 28, 2019 states he has beavers with both lodges and bank tunnels on his farm in King and Queen County, Virginia.

³⁰ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/bank%20beaver> downloaded November 16, 2018.

Depending on the type of water body they occupy, beavers construct freestanding lodges or bank dens. Lodges and bank dens are used for safety, and a place to rest, stay warm, give birth, and raise young. Freestanding lodges are built in areas where the bank or water levels aren't sufficient for a safe bank den. Bank dens are dug into the banks of streams and large ponds, and beavers may or may not build a lodge over them. Bank dens may also be located under stumps, logs, or docks.

The choice will be made based on water conditions. Beaver living in fast flowing rivers and streams that will not allow a beaver dam to be maintained simply dig a tunnel up into the bank. Usually, they will add a few dead sticks on top of the underground den

Beaver Ecology, 2012, states,

In areas prone to flooding, or where strong currents may be present, beaver usually construct bank dens by digging tunnels from underwater up into banks. Bank dens often have two or more submerged entrances. Many times, the beaver will construct a pile of sticks over the tops of the underground living chambers. These piles of sticks are sometimes called caps ... Beavers construct bank dens and lodges for shelter and raising their young. They prefer bank dens if the stream bank is suitable for construction. Starting below the water level, they dig into a stream bank, often where it's steep and held together by tree roots. Angling upward, they dig until this tunnel clears the water level by a foot or two. Beavers then hollow a chamber large enough to sleep and move around. They add one or more den entrances, fanning out in different directions. They scatter wood in the chamber

to keep it dry. They repair minor cave-ins when part of the bank collapses by piling sticks and mud on top of the hole. Beavers build lodges in marshes where the banks are too flat to dig bank dens.

After a colony is established it may have several bank burrows. One principal type of bank den has a tunnel leading from a submerged entrance up to an underground chamber located anywhere from six to fifty feet back in the bank above the water level. The tunnel varies from twelve to thirty inches in diameter (Muskrat and Beaver Management in Wetlands, 2004).

Morgan (1868:148, 157-160), who studied beavers in the Marquette area of Michigan, describes what he called "bank lodges." Morgan states:

Another, and equally common variety may be called, by way of distinction, the bank lodge. They are of two kinds. One is situated upon the bank of the stream or pond, a few feet back from its edge, and entered by an underground passage from the bed of the stream, excavated through the natural earth up into the chamber. The other is situated upon the edge of the bank, a portion of it projecting over, and resting upon the bed of the channel, so as to have the floor of the chamber rest upon the bank or on solid ground, while the external wall, on the pond side, projects beyond it, and is built up from the bottom of the pond.

Beavers are found along the Missouri River from the mountains down to the mouth of the Big Sioux, a distance of more than fifteen hundred miles. Above the mouth of the Yellowstone River, their tree cuttings are seen in great numbers...The beavers live in burrows in the banks but protect the entrances to them by a false lodge. The entrances or passage-ways often extend back twenty feet into the bank, and each communicates with one or more underground chambers which are always found near the

surface. From the extent of the cutting among the cottonwood-trees, which sometimes lay in piles upon each other, it is evident that most of the beavers inhabit the river banks.

In addition to the lodge, the same beavers, who inhabit it, have burrows in the banks surrounding the pond. They never risk their personal safety upon the lodge alone, which, being conspicuous to their enemies, is liable to attack. These burrows are the ultimate places of refuge to which they are more apt to retire than to their lodges, when disturbed on the land. Along their canals, also, the burrows are numerous, since while in their narrow channels they are more exposed than while in the ponds. These burrows are small underground chambers. They are entered by a passage-way, usually under the roots of a tree standing in the edge of a pond, which, with the chamber, are from ten to fifteen feet in length. As the entrances are always below the surface level of the pond, there are no external indications [with one exception] to mark the site of a burrow.

Based on the small number of lodges found upon the largest ponds, and a large number of burrows, Morgan (1868:164) states "it is probable that there are more beavers in every pond than the lodges can accommodate." In the Cascade Mountains, the beavers live chiefly in burrows in the banks of the streams, rarely constructing either lodges or dams. "The sides of these streams are lined with their habitations, though we never saw their houses, and seldom a dam; but usually their burrows penetrated the sides of the streams, a sufficiently large and long excavation being made to form warm, roomy, and comfortable quarters" (Williamson and Abbot, 1857:59).

Beavers bring food into the chamber in winter with debris collecting on the chamber floor. Beavers enlarge the chamber by further excavating from the ceiling and walls especially in spring. The chamber often becomes so large that the roof caves in, leaving a large hole in the ground. Beaver occupying the den are then forced to dig another chamber, but if the cave-in is not too extensive the beaver often repair the hole by covering it with limbs and covering it with mud. Beaver will continue to dig new tunnels and openings until some old bank burrows may have several adjoining tunnels each leading to a living-chamber. Such complex dens may have many openings both at the water level and below. Near a food cache beaver sometimes dig a feeding den, which is merely a pocket under the bank where the beaver feed in concealment. Beavers seldom construct lodges. Most beaver live in bank dens. Even after beaver have abandoned a pond, their burrows become homes for other kinds of wildlife (Muskrat and Beaver Management in Wetlands, 2004). Beavers have been digging into the banks of North American lakes, wetlands, and waterways for thousands of years (Lisle, 2010).

North American "Beavers often live in a dome-shaped lodge of sticks and mud, erected in much the same manner as the dam. It usually is surrounded by the water backed up by the dam. The lodge may eventually extend more than 2 meters [6.6 ft] above

the surface of the water and have a basal diameter of 12 [39.4 ft] meters" (Nowak and Paradiso, 1983:560). The internal chamber of the lodge is about 2 meters (6.6 ft) wide and a 0.6 (1.7 ft) meters high. The floor is above the water level and bedded with dry vegetation (Godin, 1977). In some areas, especially the vicinity of large rivers, beavers do not build lodges but dig dens in the banks for shelter. Tunnels of the European beaver (*Castor fiber*) may become complex and extend for more than 10 meters (32.8 ft) back and up from an entrance at or below water level (Wilsson, 1971).

Georges Cuvier, in his *Le Règne Animal* ³¹quoted in Morgan (1868:19), states,

*Two large incisors in each jaw, separated from the molars by a wide interval, cannot well seize a living prey or devour flesh. They are unable even to cut the aliment; but they serve to file, and by continued labor to reduce it into small particles; in a word, to gnaw it; hence the word rodentia applied to animals of this order; it is thus that they successfully attack the hardest substances, frequently feeding on wood and the bark of trees. The better to accomplish this object, these incisors have enamel only in front, so that their posterior edges wearing away faster than the anterior, they are always naturally sloped [or chisel like]. Their prismatic form causes them to grow from the root as fast as they wear away from the tip [their formative pulp being persistent], and this tendency to increase in length is so powerful that if either of them be lost or broken, its antagonist in the other jaw, having nothing to oppose or comminute, becomes developed to a monstrous extent.*³²

Morgan (1868:27), states,

The beaver is a burrowing animal, his normal habitation being the burrow rather than the lodge. To enable him to excavate the large chambers under ground, hereafter described, his paws are armed with claws which are long, curving, and strong. In a full-grown beaver, the claw upon the third finger measures seven-eighths of an inch [approximately 21 mm]. Those upon the hind feet are still longer and broader, and equally well adapted to assist in excavating burrows. Upon the second toe of

each hind foot there is an extra claw, set immediately under the true one and transversely. It is very thin, broad, and round edged, and projects nearly to the tip of the claw. It is peculiar to this animal.

Beavers are armed with cutting instruments, powerful incisive teeth, by means of which they are able to cut down forest trees of surprising size in comparison with their own diminutive forms. Their teeth are chisels in form and structure, and also in efficiency (Morgan, 1868:167).

The body weight of mature beaver, *Castor canadensis*, ranges on average from 16 kg (35.3 lbs) to 31.5 kg (69.4) with largest beaver weights recorded up to 39.4 kg (Hill, 1982:257, 159: Table 14.1). Average total body length including tail as much as 120 cm (3.9 ft or 47.2 in) (Hill, 1982:257).

Mountain Beaver: Aplodontia is not a beaver but also burrows into stream banks. However, the range of *Aplodontia* occurs only in the Pacific Northwest (Fellers, et al., 2016). For comparative purposes, here are published weights and lengths of mountain beaver bodies as well as dimensions of tunnels and chambers (Feldhamer and Rochelle, 1982:167, 170).

The individual mature body weight ranges from 0.8 kg (1.8 lbs) to 1.8 kg (4.0 lbs) and mature body lengths from 300 mm (11.8 in) to 500 mm (19.7 in). Tunnels range in diameter of 10 cm (3.9 in) to 20 cm (7.9 in). Chambers consist of circular-shaped nest chambers 50 cm (19 in) to 60 cm (23.6 in) in diameter and 26 cm (10.2 in) high. Feeding chambers or food caches are as large or larger. The giant beaver, *Castoroides ohioensis*, attained lengths of 1.9-2.2 m (6.2-7.2 ft) and weights of 90-125 kg (200-275 lbs) (McDonald, 1994).

³¹ *The Animal Kingdom*, new edition 1854 with additions by W.B. Carpenter and J.O. Westwood, published by W. S. Orr and Co., London.

³² See also Morgan, 1868, p. 65.

Extinct Giant Beaver: While early studies concluded that the giant beaver-felled trees and built dams as does the modern beaver (e.g., Moore, 1890; Hay, 1912; Cahn, 1932), later studies suggest that the incisors were not efficient in cutting wood and that the giant beaver probably did not, therefore, construct dams and lodges (Powell, 1948; Stirton, 1965; Holman, 1975, 1995; Kurtén and Anderson, 1980; McDonald, 1994). None of these sources mention giant beavers making bank tunnels. Hay (1923:463, Map 4) provides a map showing the distribution of giant beaver with greatest distribution just south of the Great Lakes but none reported for Maryland or Virginia. Subsequent works such as Eshelman et al. (2018:6) confirm *Castoroides* from these two states. Hulbert, et al. (2014:39, Figure 7) suggest there are two species of *Castoroides*, *C. ohioensis* and *C. dilophidus*, the later which is restricted to Florida and portions of coastal Georgia and South Carolina.

Swinhart and Richards (2001) summarize the presumed habitat of the giant beaver:

Holman (1975, 1995) related that Castoroides had a smaller brain than in Castor, suggesting that Castoroides had much less complex behavior patterns and social interactions than the latter. There is a general agreement that Castoroides thrived in lakes and ponds that were bordered by swamps (Powell 1948; Stirton 1965; Saunders 1977; Kurtén and

Anderson 1980; Harrington 1986; Holman 1995) as well as marsh habitats (Holman 1975, 1995). Most authors believe that Castoroides was a good swimmer, though was clumsy on land. Its habits have been envisioned more as those of the marsh-dwelling muskrat (Stirton 1965; Kurten & Anderson 1980), as a giant "swamp rat" moving along wide trails through the coarse vegetation of the marshy shores of a lake or across the swampy floodplain of a

glacial river (Powell 1948), or as a "large, clumsy water hog," meandering about in marshes and ponds feeding upon aquatic vegetation (Holman 1975, 1995). It is thought to have fed upon coarse leaves, the roots of sedges, cattails, and other vegetation (Powell 1948; McDonald 1994). Many authors believe that a reduction or loss of its preferred habitat at the end of the Pleistocene and perhaps its overspecialization, including the inability to disperse readily and to build dams, contributed to its extinction (Stirton 1965; Kurten & Anderson 1980; Harrington 1986; Holman 1995). Direct competition with the modern beaver may also have been involved (Powell 1948; Kurten & Anderson 1980; Holman 1995).

Harrington (1996) reports on a possible giant beaver lodge discovered near New Knoxville, Ohio, about 1912. Part of a *Castoroides* skull and the lodge were located in a peaty layer surrounded by loam. The lodge was reported to have been roughly 1.2 m (47 in) high and 2.4 m (95 in) in diameter and formed from saplings about 7.5 cm (3 in) in diameter.

Harrington (1996) suggests giant beavers seem to have preferred lakes and ponds bordered by swamps as their habitat because their remains are more commonly found in ancient swamp deposits. It should be pointed out such habitats are also more prone to preservation. Perhaps a rather sudden reduction of these surroundings due to changing climate linked with the giant beaver's apparent inability to build dams like those of *Castor canadensis* and its inability to disperse readily overland to new drainage systems when drought occurred may have resulted in its extinction and the survival of the smaller, more adaptable modern beaver.

An early Pliocene fossil locality in the Canadian High Arctic preserves the remains of the extinct beaver *Dipoides* sp. (Castoridae, Rodentia) in association with an assemblage of fossil beaver-cut wood (Rybczynski, 2008). Fossil remains of *Castoroides ohioensis* and *Castor canadensis* have been found together at several Pleistocene age localities including the Irvingtonian Sandahl local fauna of Kansas, Berends local fauna of Oklahoma; and Rancholabrean Carter local fauna of Ohio, Hartman local fauna of Pennsylvania, Ichetucknee River local fauna of Florida, Santa Fe River IIA local fauna of Florida, Old Crow River local fauna of Yukon Territory and Fairbanks II local fauna of Alaska. Although *Castoroides* and *Castor* have been recovered together in these local faunas, this does not prove giant beavers built lodges. Giant beavers may have occupied the same pond, even making use of ponds created by *Castor*. Kurtén and Anderson (1980:238) suggest the extinction of *Castoroides* might have been influenced by competition with *Castor*.

Based on stable carbon and nitrogen isotope study of bone collagen ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{col}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{col}}$) of *Castoroides*, Plint et al. (2019) determined the diet of the giant beaver was composed predominantly of macrophytes (particularly submerged macrophytes), rendering the genus highly dependent on wetland habitat for survival. Their study suggests that *Castoroides* did not share the same behaviors of tree-cutting and harvesting as did *Castor*.

Wolves: James R. Goldsberry, Maryland Wildlife Administration, and Paul Cresthull, amateur archeologist, both of whom had visited the Crofton tunnel complex, concluded the tunnels were made by wolves. The entrance to a typical wolf den is about 45.7 to 71.2 cm (~ 18 to 28 in) wide and 38.1 to 50.8 cm (15 to 20 in) high. Dens may have two or more entrances, usually marked by a large pile of excavated dirt. Den sites are often near a source of water. The birthing chamber usually lies at the end of a tunnel which may be straight, forked or hooked, and from 121.9 to 546.1 cm (4 to 18 ft) long in well-drained, soft soil typically on a south-facing slope. The birthing chamber is

usually about 50.8 cm (20 in) high by 127.0 cm (50 in) wide by 101.6 (40 in) deep. No bedding is added to the den. The birthing chamber is usually about three feet in diameter and about two feet high. It is common for wolves to use abandoned dens of other animals, such as bear dens or a beaver lodge. Wolves often enlarge existing coyote or fox dens (Anonymous, 2018, Wolf Ecology and Behavior: Wolf Dens).

Verdict: Who Made the Tunnel Complex?

As noted above, there is no evidence the tunnels were made by humans. Earl H. Hodil, Assistant Director of the Maryland Wildlife Administration, is believed to be the first person to suggest the tunnel complex was made by bank beavers based on the description given by Bastian to him on July 24, 1973 (1973:9). Independent of Hodil's assertion, Robert L. Humphry, Jr. Chairman, Department of Anthropology, Smithsonian Institution and George Stuart, an archeologist with National Geographic Society, visited the tunnel complex on July 25 and both concluded the tunnels were probably dug by beavers (Bastian, 1973:9).

Doepkens et al., Figure 8 (1979:13, Diagram 2) show that all the tunnels slope upward from the swamp and at least seven of the twenty tunnels had entrances under water. Wolf den tunnels would not have underwater entrances. While it is possible wolves may have re-occupied the Crofton Tunnel Complex, the incisor tooth marks on the walls and chambers are flat like a beaver incisor, not sharp like a wolf canine. Wolf canines, not incisors, if used for digging, would leave a V-shaped mark. The V-shaped marks on the Crofton Tunnel compare well to claw digging marks, not carnivore canine tooth marks Cresthull obtained casts and photos of the Crofton tooth marks from which he attempted to make an identification with references to the literature (Bastian, 1973:12). It is unclear the results of his work but clearly, the Crofton tooth marks are not those of a wolf or any other carnivore.

Clayton Ray, Curator of Pleistocene Mammals, Department of Paleobiology, National Museum of Natural History; Smithsonian Institution, was contacted by Bastian by phone on July 22nd. Bastian (1973:5) states that “Ray could not think of any geologically recent animal in the Maryland area that would dig rooms and tunnels of the size and extent which I described.” After visiting the tunnel complex Ray believed the Crofton burrows were most likely made by modern *Castor*. He suggested that beaver tunnel complexes used over many generations get larger over time. Clayton suggested the prevalence of damming and lodges versus tunnels was due to trapping pressure.³³ Dr. Ray may have been misquoted in a newspaper article as saying the tunnels were dug by *Castoroides*. Ray indicated that Doepkens was not pleased with his identification because at this time Doepkens was convinced the tunnels were dug by “extinct” beavers.³⁴

Modern beavers have prominently ridged chisel-like incisor teeth for gnawing on wood, while the incisor of the giant beaver *Castoroides* was bigger, broader and blunt with rounded tips that grew to about 15 cm (6 in) long. These incisors were not as efficient at cutting wood, therefore it is interpreted that the giant beaver did not cut trees to construct dams and lodges.

Conclusions

In addition to Bastian’s (1973) narrative report on the investigations, there are two versions of Doepkens’ 1979 self-published report on the tunnel complex. The first report is titled “Excavations of an Extinct Native

Maryland Beaver Complex at Crofton, AA Co., Maryland,” by William P. Doepkens. The second later version published the same year is “Beavers of Crofton, Maryland” by William P. Doepkens et al. (1979).³⁵ The titles make it clear that Doepkens initially believed the tunnels were made by the

extinct giant beaver *Castoroides* even after the scientists from the Smithsonian Institution determined the tooth marks were made by the common North American beaver *Castor*. Doepkens states the following in the first paragraph of his report (1979a; 1979b):

It seems unfortunate that in modern times when the past is beginning to be viewed as the key to the future, a discovery as unique as the extinct beaver habitat at Crofton, Anne Arundel Co., Md. could go unstudied by the scientists. At a time when scientists are willing to travel around the world to track down a hunch, it is distressing that such an unusual opportunity to study a backyard discovery should be passed up.

After more consideration, Doepkens et al. (1979) revised his opinion and agreed that the tooth marks were the result of *Castor*, thus the revised second and much-curtailed report with a new title.

Bastian (1973:7) states,

I concluded that the small diameter of the tunnels, the absence of artifacts, the consistently near-vertical orientation of the digging makes, the lack of indication of any material for which mining by tunneling would have been practical, and the lack of debris in the tunnels made it extremely unlikely that the tunnels were made by men (or children). The vertically undulating pattern of the tunnels and the lack of any apparent erosion from water seemed to make underground water an unlikely explanation. Glaser...stated that they were not of geological origin. Burrowing animals seemed to be the only remaining

³³ David Bohaska phone communication with Dr. Clayton Ray and email communication to Eshelman July 6, 2018.

³⁴ David Bohaska phone communication with Dr. Clayton Ray and email communication to Eshelman July 6, 2018

³⁵ Co-author Eric Dennard was an art instructor at Key School. It is presumed he did the drawing of a beaver found on the cover and title page of the report as well as probably the drawings of the tunnel cross-sections and plan view of the tunnel complex.

alternative...there was no possibility of a hoax...

Doepkens (1979a:29) states,

Having been stopped by construction, we feel that a vast amount of knowledge was lost by not being able to explore the entire complex. What we explored was only a small portion of the vast networks of tunnels and chambers dug within the hillside. From all indications, the native Maryland beaver dug the enormous tunnel and chamber system with the use of claws, as well as incisors...The single most important fact that emerged from all of our work, is the fact that beaver do indeed use their incisors as extensive digging tools.

Note in the title of his report Doepkens used the words "Extinct Native Maryland Beaver," and he probably meant "extinct" here as well.

The size and shape of the Crofton Tunnel Complex tooth marks plus the absence of any indication of parallel enamel ridge grooves on the anterior face of the incisor marks indicate the tunnel complex tooth marks were made by *Castor*, not *Castoroides*. Based on the measurements given by Bastian and estimated measurements based on the scaled photographs and on the cast, as well as the incisor shape and enamel pattern, the tooth marks are those of the common beaver *Castor*. While the tunnels and dens are complex, and the size of some of the rooms are larger than expected, the overall characteristics, complexity, and size compare favorably with *Castor*. The tunnels and dens were made by the North American beaver *Castor canadensis* and they date from the Holocene Epoch, probably from the early historic period. The Crofton Tunnel Complex is the largest and among the best example of a beaver claw and incisor dug tunnel and den complex presently known. The Miocene *Paleocastor* cork-screw burrows from the Harrison Formation of Nebraska also preserve incisor and claw marks (Martin and Bennett, 1977). Similar to the Crofton Tunnel Complex, claw

marks are more confined to the sides of the tunnels and incisor marks to top of the tunnels. *Procastor* tunnels are known to extend 4.6 m (15 ft.).

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